

INTEGRATION OF LEARNING ANALYTICS INTO A LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM BASED ON A MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHM

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Abstract

The article substantiates the relevance of the application of educational methods of Data Mining, arising within the framework of the educational process, to study the implementation of the educational program. There are many benefits of using learning management systems (LMS), including cost reduction, content management, flexibility, and etc. Despite these significant advantages of using LMS, the traditional LMS system cannot support modern learning needs. In particular, extracting useful information from huge educational data, analyzing and interpreting this information is a difficult task. Learning analytics can effectively address these needs in terms of predicting student performance, engagement, and potential problems. This study presents learning analytics using machine learning techniques and examines its integration into LMS. In this work, machine learning methods are used to demonstrate the process of learning analytics and forecasting the implementation of an educational program using educational data.

Keywords: Educational Data Analysis, Learning Analytics, Machine Learning, Linear Regression, LMS.

Introduction

In the modern world, education is considered as the most important component of economic growth and development of the state. Its role for man and society is constantly increasing. Modern man lives and acts in conditions that require high professionalism and significant intellectual efforts to make the right decisions in various life and professional situations. An increase in information flows, their versatility, a clear lack of time to comprehend them, increased competitiveness.

Education is no longer just the teaching of texts or the requirement to memorize manuscripts. The learning process, both in and outside the classroom, has become an activity with measurable goals and results. Over time, educational methods have become a dynamic part of the input and output data of the learning process. Moreover, these practices have become a vital part, playing an important role in expanding the promotion of the components of the learning system, updating the foundations of the curriculum and increasing its effectiveness and ingenuity. These components are used in the process of planning, implementation, evaluation, follow-up and goal development [6].

Many universities have large repositories of unused collected data that can provide both informative and effective feedback. With growing concerns about career readiness and academic success, much of higher education has recognized the powerful potential of learning analytics to predict student performance and identify at-risk students at an early stage. Decision-making in the field of education is a complex, multidimensional process involving a large range of stakeholders. An important criterion for making an effective decision is the analysis of information received from participants in the educational process at its various stages.

The collection, analysis, interpretation and use of data accumulated in the course of educational activities is a rather complex and time-consuming process. Currently existing scientific areas related to the analysis of educational data, such as intellectual analysis of educational data Educational Data Mining (EDM) and educational analytics - Learning Analytics (LA) are relatively new areas and require the creation of a methodology and appropriate tools.

Educational Data Mining (EDM) is the process of using data mining techniques to analyze educational data [1]. EDM is a field of research that focuses on the

development of algorithms and techniques for analyzing large datasets generated by educational systems [2]. The purpose of EDM is to improve teaching and learning by identifying patterns and trends in educational data [3]. EDM involves the use of statistical and machine learning algorithms to analyze educational data such as student performance, learning styles, and engagement patterns. Data can be collected from a variety of sources, such as learning management systems, online learning platforms, and educational games. The data is then preprocessed, transformed and analyzed to extract meaningful information [4].

The ability to collect data in LMS and information systems the university opens up new horizons for data mining researchers in the field of education who can extract deeper information. EDM tries to extract patterns from the data generated during the learning process. This data can be very extensive and contain a large number of details. Recently, EDM has been used within higher education to improve learning strategies. EDM involves the use of statistics, visualization, and machine learning techniques to explore and analyze educational data.

EDM is closely related to Learning analytics. Learning Analytics (LA) is a relatively new field and has been used a lot and has been very influential in higher education in many aspects.

The goals and objectives of research in these disciplines largely coincide. Learning Analytics (LA) is a new field of research aimed at improving the quality of education [1], [2]. LA is an analytical approach aimed at analyzing, measuring and extracting comprehensive information about a student on various characteristics, including cognitive, social and psychological aspects, to help teachers make decisions about the student's successes and failures [1],[2].

At the moment, the development of artificial intelligence technologies provides machine learning with significant interest from the educational sector. Combining many complex approaches and mathematical algorithms, machine learning is becoming in demand in many areas of human life. It is effective for data analysis, understanding the pattern and correlation between data for forecasting. In particular, ML can learn from the data to find rules and patterns so that it can predict future action. LA requires extracting useful information from large sets of educational data and correlating the data for various purposes.

Classical machine learning algorithms are divided into two main groups: supervised learning algorithms ("supervised algorithms") and unsupervised learning algorithms ("unsupervised algorithms"). The principle of learning algorithms with a teacher is that the input receives information, as well as the required results. This way, the machine can find out what the user expects it to output when a similar command is entered.

Concepts the prospect of using machine learning in the field of education and pedagogical technologies:

- forecasting student academic performance;
- optimization of the student assessment process;
- creation of an individual educational route;
- processing and adaptation of educational materials;

– support for teachers and staff of educational institutions.

ML is the study of computer algorithms that are improved automatically by specifying and using data (training) [5]. The value of machine learning algorithms depends on the quality of the data used for its training and deployment. Universities are responsible for creating or obtaining enough data to ensure that this data is useful for a particular algorithm and that a group of analysts can sort them and extract useful things from them [6].

This paper proposes learning analytics models for integration into an existing LMS. LMS typically stores a large amount of educational data, and learning analytics can extract and process this data to meet the various needs of stakeholders. The proposed LA feeds data from an existing LMS and uses metrics such as gender, age, location, higher education, grades, and machine learning (ML) techniques for forecasting purposes.

In this article, the proposed learning analytics focuses on existing student data from LMS and uses ML methods for descriptive and diagnostic analysis. The research mainly focuses on predicting student academic performance so that educational institutions can take diagnostic measures to identify potential problems.

The methodology of the experiment

The purpose of Learning Analytics (LA) is to collect data from various sources and analyze data for various purposes to meet the needs of stakeholders in terms of forecasts or identifying potential problems. In this way, the LMS system stores various data related to student enrollment, progression, and other relevant areas. Therefore, LMS data can be used as one of the main inputs for LA. However, the data stored in the LMS is in different formats with different levels of structure from different sources. Therefore, it is extremely important to integrate the data into a consistent and meaningful format.

This section will describe one of the analytical methods for selecting attributes and extracting information parameters. To do this, it is necessary to properly prepare the data for processing, choose the appropriate method for extracting the desired patterns and, finally, determine how to evaluate the found patterns, these stages are organized into a scheme known as the knowledge Data Discovery process (KDD – Knowledge Data Discovery), where EDM is used at one of the main stages, a brief explanation of the KDD process, describing each of the stages.

The KDD process is a non—trivial process of identifying valid, new and potentially useful patterns in a dataset, that is, the goal is to find useful, valid, relevant and new knowledge about a particular activity. The term "nontrivial" is understood as some kind of search or inference, that is, it involves the search for models, structures, patterns or parameters [7], [8].

This process consists of several phases and includes database methods, machine learning (ML), statistics, artificial intelligence and decision-making systems.

In the study, the KDD process is used to integrate learning analytics into LMS to determine the impact of learning outcomes from a number of disciplines from different cycles of educational programs on student academic performance.

Properly implemented learning analytics can use data mining technologies and statistical modeling to analyze educational data such as undergraduate grade

point average (GPA) or current grades to make informed predictions. Teachers can use learning analytics to solve problems and optimize the learning process. Consequently, the central proposal of this new field is to simplify the ways in which educational data is collected, synthesized, and reported, and to provide support for student academic success.

Figure 1. Integration of learning analytics in LMS.

Figure 1 shows a conceptual view of the integration of learning analytics in LMS. It includes sequential steps to collect, prepare, and finally classify a dataset using machine learning models. We have completed three separate steps: 1) Data collection and integration 2) Data analysis and transformation 3) Prediction. The steps are explained below:

Step 1. Data collection and integration: At this stage, it is necessary to identify the data sources, which in itself is already a difficult task, and then select the data. Data collection is the first step of the LA process. It collects and integrates data from various sources related to all stages of the student's life cycle. Data collection is usually carried out using data collected from various sources related to enrollment, engagement, performance, and student feedback. The choice of data sources depends on the purpose of the analysis. The relevant data can be extracted using a CSV file or XML, and the data will come from multiple platforms.

Step 2. Data Analysis and Transformation (DAT): Once the data is extracted, the next step is data analysis. The purpose of this stage is to analyze and clean up the data if necessary. This will help to improve the accuracy of the results. At this stage, the selected data set is organized into a manageable form, which is necessary for the next stage. Machine learning requires only those variables that actually affect the final result. The selection of features is performed here. This is a procedure for discarding insignificant variables from a purified sample before launching machine learning and educational data mining. Reducing the number of predictors is necessary for several reasons:

- significance of features — as a rule, the initial sample always contains a lot of "garbage data": noise, emissions, and only a few predictors affect the real result [10];
- accuracy of the solution — some Machine Learning models are sensitive to the magnitude of the input vector. For example, neural networks with a large number of input data can lead to retraining [11];
- Calculation speed — the fewer variables, the faster the calculations will go.

Data transformation involves preprocessing data and generating new variables from existing ones. At

this stage, the focus is on normalizing the various features and data selected for the study in order to standardize all data at similar scales, thus avoiding bias problems due to the wide range of values for certain variables.

Step 3. Forecasting: This final stage of the LA process provides context-based analysis and reporting of the collected data to understand the patterns needed for forecasting. Here, an attempt is made to determine the relationship between the input elements and the output elements. The selected features from the DA step affect the prediction.

At this stage, algorithmic ML methods with appropriately controlled techniques are used to implement learning analytics: classification and regression, decision trees (DT), ensemble models (EM), k-nearest neighbors (KNN), logistic regression (LR), naive Bayes (NB), random forest (RF) and auxiliary vector machines (SVM); or an uncontrolled method: artificial neural networks (ANN), clustering (CLU) and correlation analysis [12,13]. In the case of ANN, they are also very popular controlled methods in ML.

One of the simplest and most useful ML models, linear regression, was used for the study. Linear regression is a machine learning algorithm that is mainly used to perform regression analysis.

This is a model of the dependence of variable x on one or more other variables (factors, regressors, independent variables) with a linear dependence function.

Simple Linear Regression Analysis is to find the relationship between two continuous variables: the independent variable (the predictor) on the x -axis with the dependent variable (the outcome variable) on the vertical axis. y . Then draw a regression line and from this line equation we can predict the variable y in general form [14]

$$y = w_0 + w_1 * x \quad (1)$$

Where x is the predictor variable, y is the value predicted with the corresponding x value (response variable). To determine the values of w_0 and w_1 , we use the least squares formula to get a most suitable straight line. The calculations w_0 and w_1 are as follows:

this stage, the data was converted from XLS format to CSV format and Python libraries such as NumPy, Pandas were used for data processing.

At the forecasting stage, a one-dimensional linear regression model was chosen as a model for the ratio of

values between the array of predictors and the performance evaluation vector, the parameters of which were calculated based on data on student academic performance.

Full name	Political science	Cultural studies	Social recognition	Modern history of Kazakhstan	Programming language Python	GPA
Abdualieva Akmaral	96	99	99	99	85	3,18
Aytkul Uldana	97	100	100	100	97	3,51
Alabek Uldana Talgatkyzy	99	98	97	100	78	3,05
Alakerim Arailym Kerimkhanovna	98	100	99	99	88	3,17
Balikbay Kuandyk Sakenuly	96	99	99	100	72	2,82
Bekmurat Nurila Gabitovna	100	99	100	99	95	3,12
Georgy Belyakov Vitalievich	84	70	87	58	84	2,96
Simuratova Bibinur Bidatkakyy	100	100	98	99	75	3,37
Dostayeva Dilyara Sukhrabovna	98	99	100	98	86	3,13
Femys Dinmukhammad Bizhanuly	100	99	95	100	87	2,9
Iaqs?l?q Qaz?na Jold?bekq?z?	100	100	99	99	85	3,07
Ianbyr Shugyla Bekmuratkizy	100	99	97	99	100	3,13
Zholdasbek Aktolkyn Aldiyarkizy	100	99	98	99	91	3,11
Zhumabay Marzhan Temurkyzy	95	100	98	98	95	3,05
Zhuruntai Tazakul Galymkyzy	90	83	85	100	84	3,28
Kazbek Daniyar Kanatuly	98	100	97	98	76	2,73
Kenzhe Dana Erlanovna	98	80	90	95	95	3,08
Kurmanbayev Daniyar Tlektesyly	99	100	75	98	95	2,86
Mamraim Guldaria Sabitovna	94	99	91	97	88	3,01
Nametzhan Balnur Maksatkyzy	93	100	96	100	82	3
Pernebay Bekzat Maratovich	100	100	98	100	81	2,94
Polathan Nurkeldi Izbasaruly	100	98	94	98	65	2,84
Seit Asylzhan Arapovich	97	100	97	98	75	2,84
Turlybay Aigerim Batyrbayevna	99	99	98	100	83	3,44
Jsenbay Aruna Artikkizy	92	97	98	98	78	3,14

Figure 3. CSV file the student's average score

The objective linear regression function consists of one feature X, where the feature is the academic performance scores for the discipline of one of the cycles: general education subjects, basic subjects, profile subjects, and the target variable Y is the average bachelor's degree score (GPA) Fig. 4.

```
Ввод [2]: import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
data = pd.read_csv('RegressionL8.csv', sep=';')
data.head()
```

```
Out[2]:
```

	X1	Y
0	52	2,19
1	56	2,58
2	56	2,09
3	58	2,96
4	58	2,33

Figure 4. Data for visualization.csv.

Python was used to demonstrate experiments and obtain graphs [15] (Fig.5).

To eliminate over-training to the conditions of the problem, additional restrictions were added in order to build an algorithm that minimizes error and the number of variables used. The study used L1 regularization (Lasso regression) and L2 ridge regression [15] (Fig.5)

Figure 5. Polynomial regressions with L2 and L1 regularization.

The free coefficients of the empirical linear regression model with L1 and L2 regularization are presented in the form of a graph.

Figure 6. a) Free coefficients of the objective function of linear regression with L2 regularization (in ridge regression) $w_0 = 1.1$, $w_1 = 0.25$ for the cycle of basic subjects OP, b) Free coefficients of the objective function of linear regression with regularization L1 (in Lasso regression) $w_0 = 2.8$, $w_1 = 0.12$ for the cycle of general education subjects.

A linear regression model helps predict the value of a dependent variable, and can also help explain how accurate the forecast is. This is determined by the values of the parameters of the free coefficients. The value of w_1 indicates how much of the variation of the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable. The values of w_1 range from 0 to 1. A value of 0.12 means that the independent variable can explain 12 percent of the change in the observed values of the dependent variable. A value of 1 means that an ideal forecast can be made, which is rare in practice. A value of 0 means that the independent variable does not help at all in predicting the dependent variable.

Figure 7. The impact of subjects on student academic performance

A linear regression forecasting model $y=2.8+0.12x$ was obtained, and it was found that the results of teaching «Modern History of Kazakhstan»

from the cycle of general education subjects have a 12% impact on student academic performance. In addition, it can be concluded that the results of teaching

basic subjects, such as «Math1», «Math2», affect the results of students' GPA by 25% according to the forecasting model, in which $y=1.31+0.25x$. The results of teaching the core subjects «Programming languages», «Methods of teaching computer science» have an impact on student academic performance by 32% according to the model $y=1.2+0.32x$ Fig. 7.

These research results can be used in the development of an educational program and forecasting student academic performance. Our findings will help strengthen the importance of integrating learning analytics into student management and curriculum development. It will also help you understand how feature selection improves the performance of machine learning models.

Conclusion

Learning analytics has received huge attention from academic communities because of its proposal to interpret education data. Thus, the advantages of learning analytics and its integration into LMS are already widely known. It can also provide real-time early warning related to student engagement and progression so that organizations can take the necessary proactive measures. In this work, we used machine learning methods to demonstrate the process of integrating learning analytics into LMS and predicting the implementation of an educational program. Understanding linear regression is the key to understanding more complex models, right down to deep neural networks. As a future work, we will integrate more features such as student usage data, attendance records for other forecasts.

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References:

1. R. Baker, "Data mining for education," in *International Encyclopedia of Education*, B. McGaw, P. Peterson, and E. Baker, Eds., 3rd ed. Oxford, U.K.: Elsevier, 2010.
2. R. S. J. D. Baker and G. Siemens, "Educational Data Mining and Learning Analytics," in *Cambridge Handbook of the Learning Sciences*, 2014, pages 253 – 272 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139519526.016>
3. David L. la Red Martínez, Carlos E. Podestá

Gómez. Contributions from Data Mining to Study Academic Performance of Students of a Tertiary Institute. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 2014, Vol. 2, No.9, pages 713-726. doi: 10.12691/education-2-9-3.

4. Du, X., Yang, J., Hung, J. L., & Shelton, B. (2020). Educational data mining: a systematic review of research and emerging trends. *Information Discovery and Delivery*, 2020, Vol 48, No 4, pages 225-236. DOI:10.1108/IDD-09-2019-0070
5. Berry, M.; Linoff, G. *Big Data, Data Mining, and Machine Learning: Value Creation for Business Leaders and Practitioners*; New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 19976.
6. KDD in data mining assists data prep for machine learning [Electronic resource] — Available: <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpriseai/feature/KDD-in-data-mining-assists-data-prep-for-machine-learning> (date of application: 12/17/2023).
7. Fayyad, U., Piatetsky-Shapiro, G., & Smyth, P. (1996). From Data Mining to Knowledge Discovery in Databases. *AI Magazine*, Vol.17, Issue 3, pages 37-54. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1609/aimag.v17i3.1230>
8. Adhikari, A.; Adhikari, J. *Advances in Knowledge Discovery in Databases.*- New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2015.
9. Debuse, J.; de la Iglesia, B.; Howard, C.; Raymond-Smith, V. *Building the KDD Roadmap.* In *Industrial Knowledge Management*; Roy,R., Ed.- London, UK:Springer, 2001.
10. Evaluation and selection of variables for machine learning models. Available: <https://www.mql5.com/ru/articles/2029>(date of application: 12/17/2023).
11. Feature selection methods. Available: <https://habr.com/ru/post/264915> /(date of application: 10/28/2023).
12. Tan, P.; Steinbach, M.; Karpatne, A.; Kumar, V. *Introduction to Data Mining.* -Delhi, India: Pearson Education, 2018.
13. Hastie, T.; Tibshirani, R. *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction.*- New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2016.
14. Linear Regression for Machine Learning. Available: <https://machinelearningmastery.com/linear-regression-for-machine-learning/>(date of application: 10/28/2023).
15. Basic principles of machine learning on the example of linear regression. Available: <https://habr.com/ru/companies/ods/articles/322076> /(date of application: 12/17/2023).